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LINGUO-DIDACTIC ASPECT OF FORMATION OF THE PROFESSIONALLY-ORIENTED LEXICAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS OF THE SPECIALTY “JURISPRUDENCE”

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У статті наголошується на тому, що сформована лексична компетентність передбачає оволодіння студентами значеннями лексичної одиниці, її написанням і вимовою, знанням граматичних форм слова, синонімів і антонімів і оволодінням правилами сполучуваності з іншими лексичними одиницями. Вправи є невід’ємною частиною формування та вдосконалення професійно орієнтованої лексичної компетентності. Вони використовуються на етапах формування та вдосконалення лексичних умінь і навичок.

Навчання іношомовної професійно орієнтованої лексики студентів юридичних факультетів побудовано на загально-дидактичних принципах (доступності; науковості; свідомості; активності; систематичності; послідовності і міцності засвоєння знань, умінь і навичок; наочності) і методичних принципах (стимулювання і мотивації позитивного ставлення до процесу навчання іноземної мови для спеціальних цілей; врахування індивідуальних особливостей студентів; професійної спрямованості навчання іношомовної лексики; обліку ступеня професійної підготовки студентів та відповідності змісту іношомовного лексичного матеріалу потребам майбутньої професійної діяльності); принципі системного засвоєння професійно орієнтованого лексичного матеріалу на основі комплексу некоммуникативних і умовно-коммуникативних вправ при взаємопов’язаному вдосконаленні навичок та умінь читання, усного та писемного мовлення за професійним спрямуванням, оскільки формування професійно орієнтованої лексичної компетентності має бути організовано за допомогою комплексу вправ, в якому реалізуються основні принципи і зміст навчання. Формування професійно орієнтованої лексичної компетентності впливає на вдосконалення і розвиток іношомовної професійно орієнтованої комунікативної компетентності в цілому. Від рівня сформованості лексичної компетентності залежить уміння читати і розуміти професійно орієнтовану літературу та здійснювати професійне спілкування.

Загалом, в контексті сучасного змісту освіти увага повинна приділятися, передусім, новим стандартам, основна ідея яких має базуватися на компетентнісному підході, що включатиме формування загальних компетентностей і потреби ринку праці. Зупинити відтік майбутніх чи практикуючих правознавців, – то це тільки якістю вищої освіти, яка невпинно зростає, яка спрямована на очікування ринку праці, та працює на випередження. Сьогодні мову необхідно вести про обов’язковість формування загальних компетентностей, готовність до тих викликів, які можуть з’явитися упродовж найближчого часу

Ключові слова: лексична компетентність, лексичні навички, іношомовна лексика, професійно орієнтований текст, освіта протягом життя

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1. Introduction

Law students need to master various types of professionally-oriented speaking activities and, above all, reading authentic specialized literature with the direct acquisition of professionally relevant information, needed to engage in the professional communication that supports motivation, because it is a source of credible, professional data communicative skills, that allows to use foreign language freely in the professional activity [1]. The choice of a lexical material depends directly on the relevance of texts and linguistic situations to the professional interests of future professionals, so the content and organization of foreign language learning will vary according to the studied specialty.

2. Literature overview

The problem of teaching professionally oriented vocabulary quite widely has been covered in the modern methodology. Most studies address this problem through

the study of reading literature according to the specialty [2, 3]. The issues of learning an active vocabulary of different specialties have been developed [4, 5]. An attempt to use a functional approach to the selection and organization of linguistic material, as well as to the organization of the educational process using models of typical situations and types of social contacts, inherent in the professional activity of lawyers, has been made [6]. Different approaches to defining the content and structure of such concepts as "competence" and "competence approach" have been analyzed, the peculiarities of the content and structure of lexical competence as a component of professional training of future lawyers have been considered [7]. However, the issue of the professionally-oriented lexical competence in law students is not fully resolved. In this regard, the teaching environment quite clearly recognized the need for the further improvement of law students' professionally oriented lexical competence formation methods.

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The aim of the study is to develop a methodology for the formation of the law specialties students' professionally oriented lexical competence in the process of learning English.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks have been set:

1) to determine the peculiarities of the professionally oriented lexical competence formation in higher educational establishments of the law profile;

2) to identify the objectives, content, principles and conditions of the law students' professionally oriented lexical competence formation.

4. Vectors of the professionally oriented lexical competence formation.

The hypothesis of the study shows that the principle of systematic mastering of the professionally oriented vocabulary, based on a set of non-communicative and conditionally-communicative exercises in the interrelated improvement of reading, oral and written vocational skills, is important for the research. However, the formation of the professionally oriented lexical competence should be organized with the help of an exercises set, in which the basic principles and content of the training have been implemented. Thus, the memorization level of the professionally oriented vocabulary in the process of reading will increase, and therefore, the process of law students professionally oriented lexical competence formation will be more effective in terms of the number of lexical units, learned by students in the course of doing exercises and time, spent on their learning, if the training takes into account the features of the law vocabulary and rely on the professional competence of law students.

5. Results of the study and their discussion.

Practical proficiency in a foreign-language vocationally oriented vocabulary means that those who learn can correlate a visual image with semantics, differentiate similar word forms on informative grounds, differentiate homonymous, synonymous, antonymic phenomena, to have the skills of receptive combining and recombining a new and previously learned lexical material, to use a word-making and contextual conjecture [8].

The main components of the linguistic competence are grammatical and lexical competences [9]. The lexical competence is a person's ability to define the contextual meaning of a word, to compare the meaning of the word in two languages, to understand the structure of the meaning of the word and to distinguish specifically the national meaning of the word. This ability is "based on lexical knowledge, skills, and personal and linguistic experience of a person" [10]. The law professional's vocabulary is a collection of words and phrases of any language. It is the most important part of the language material, largely defining the content of learning. The form of a word implies its "sound form, without which it is impossible to correctly understand the word from hearing and adequately sound it itself, and also a graphic form, without which a word will not be identified in reading and cannot be written" [11]. If a word has some peculiarities of grammatical forms formation, then it should be reported to students already at the stage of familiariza-

tion, in order to avoid mistakes in further use of the given word. For the formation of lexical skills, the establishment of strong paradigmatic association of words is necessary, because these connections provide strength of memorization, and therefore the immediate recall of words from the long-term memory. Without this skill, word pairing with each other at syntagmatic relations may be useless. Ensuring constant updating of the learned vocabulary and its maximum rotation is the main factor that provides increased semantic fields. The enrichment of the active vocabulary (the vocabulary that a person constantly uses in the oral language communication) should not be done due to the mechanical introduction of the new vocabulary, but due to the creative use of already learned, but in new contexts.

In order to make the formation of the professionally oriented lexical competence much more effective, it is necessary to take into account the correlation of the form and meaning of the lexical unit in the native language and foreign and possible interference of the studied word. Furthermore, it is faster and easier to learn such groups of words as: international and borrowed words, the meaning of which is the same in two languages; derivatives and compound words, whose components are familiar to students; root words, whose range of meanings in both languages does not contradict each other.

First of all, law texts and professional communication are characterized by the presence of a special language (special vocabulary), which is used by specialists of a particular field of activity (professionalism and terms). Special vocabulary is a combination of words and phrases that name objects and concepts, related to different spheres of human employment and are not commonly used [12]. The vocabulary rich in terms and professionalism is a characteristic feature of the language for special purposes.

In the given context, the principle of systematic mastery of professionally oriented vocabulary, based on a set of non-communicative and conditionally communicative exercises in the interrelated improvement of the skills of reading, speaking and writing in a professional direction, has been emphasized. Because the formation of the professionally oriented lexical competence should be organized with the help of an exercises set, in which the basic principles and content of training have been implemented [13]. In the process of making exercises it is necessary to take into account: the stage of skills development and formation in the selection of exercises and in determining their sequence; the native language of instructions both in terms of interference and in terms of possible positive transfer; the purpose in determining the required set of exercises; specific learning conditions and language material in determining the ratio of different types of exercises; gradual increase in difficulty in performing a certain set of exercises.

There are four stages to the formation of the lexical competence:

1) the mastering of a word at a paradigmatic level for the formation of a sound, motor and graphic image of the word, based on auditory exercises;

2) the formation of the meaning of a word at the syntagmatic level in order to establish the connections

that the word may intervene in (constructing phrases with the lexical units under study);

3) the development of the meaning of a word at the syntactic level while composing sentences with the fulfilled word combinations;

4) the improvement of the ability to choose the best value depending on a communication situation and the ability to match the context to that value when listening and speaking [14].

The use of visual aids for the introduction and consolidation of the vocabulary, the development of a typology of vocabulary exercises in professionally oriented reading in a foreign language, the definition of a professionally oriented lexical minimum contributes to the teaching of reading literature in the specialty. Different visual aids, definitions, context have been used in acquaintance with the professionally oriented vocabulary.

At the stage of introducing a new lexical material, there should also be an initial attachment of this material through non-communicative exercises, such as: compare a word with its definition in Ukrainian or English; translate international the words into Ukrainian; translate words into words using word-forming elements; replace the Ukrainian words in a foreign language with the appropriate English words (select from a range of words) etc. The formation of knowledge, skills and competences is the purpose of the second stage of working with the professionally oriented vocabulary. At the stage of training a foreign language professionally oriented vocabulary one should use non-communicative and conditionally-communicative exercises, aimed at learning the lexical material (i.e. the assimilation of the form and meaning of the new lexical unit). These exercises include: differential exercises, aimed at highlighting the common and distinctive features of studied lexical units; imitative (repetitive) exercises, used primarily to memorize the graphic and sound form of new vocabulary units, as well as to create associations; substitutive (constructive) exercises, used to automate the mechanism of choice in constructing messages by analogy, when new lexical units are used in already known grammatical structures; transformational exercises that involve a specific transformation of a replica or part thereof, aimed at replacing, expanding or reducing it; reproductive exercises that involve students, reproducing replicas with learned lexical units.

The consolidation of vocationally oriented vocabulary skills has been realized through the implementation of exercises such as: select the appropriate words from the list; replace the highlighted words with words in the list; replace the selected words with synonyms, homonyms and antonyms; rephrase this sentence using new words; give an interpretation of these terms; write down possible combinations of data below words; fill in the blanks with the relevant words; replace the selected words with synonymous words in the list; make your own definitions before the deadline and more.

At the third final stage, the tasks should be aimed at comparing, generalizing, isolating, semantizing different tasks of the linguistic, speech, professional character that bring the language activity closer to a future specialist activity. Performing communication exercises at this stage involves the great creative activity of students: make a plan of read or listen to the text; give detailed

answers to questions on a particular topic, using new words; annotate the text; translate the text; complete the sentence; select the facts that confirm or deny them from the text and add your own; make instructions; prepare a monologue for the topic, including the new vocabulary and more.

The effective practical use of the language is ensured by a set of communication exercises, role-playing games, language situations, professional discussions, competitions, quizzes, conferences, stimulating the interest of students and their active creative activity in mastering a foreign language with a focus on solving communicative professional tasks that involve the involuntary memorization of the lexical material. Communication exercises are aimed at the use of the learned lexical material in the language and are close to the natural process of communication. They are characterized by generality, irreducibility, automation and dynamism, and can be performed with the emphasis on keywords, pictures, subject, text, and situation. The following exercises include: exercises in the description (describe an object, prepare an annotation, make an instruction, prepare a report, etc.); exercises in the expression of an attitude, evaluation (express an own attitude towards a scientific discovery, explain a scientific fact, prove an own point of view, refute a point of view of an interlocutor); translations of texts in their own words (using the new vocabulary), etc.

Thus, the formed lexical competence involves students' mastering of meanings of a lexical unit, its spelling and pronunciation, knowledge of grammatical forms of words, synonyms and antonyms, and mastering the rules of compatibility with other lexical units. Exercises are an integral part of the formation and improvement of the professionally oriented vocabulary competence. They are used in the stages of formation and improvement of lexical skills. However, it is important to keep in mind that to ensure the organization of the learning process requires a systematic exercise, most of which students can and must perform independently at a convenient pace and at a convenient time for them, which is primarily due to the reduction in the number of classroom hours. As a result, with the interaction of these learning factors, the process of lexical competence formation can become much more efficient.

Certainly, in the context of the Continuing Education or Lifelong Learning paradigm, it should be emphasize on key aspects, in particular, the enhancement of the role of the student's personality, on purposeful education, which is carried out on a continuous basis in order to improve knowledge, skills and competences.

Increasing the quality of education and ensuring the quality of education will stop the outflow of specialists. According to the above context it follows, that identifying a priority area for change is important for improving the quality of education: mechanisms for quality assurance of education are still practically absent in Ukraine; integration into the European Higher Education and Research Areas; the formation and development of lifelong learning, which is now in its infancy in Ukraine. Particular attention should be paid to the contemporary content of education, the standards of which should be based on a competency-based approach and include the formation of common competencies and the needs of the

labor market, and be prepared for the challenges that may arise in the near future.

6. Conclusions

1. The formation of the professionally oriented lexical competence influences the formation, improvement and development of the foreign language professionally oriented communicative competence as a whole. The level of lexical competence has been determined by the ability to read and understand professionally oriented literature and to communicate in a professional way.

2. A methodological typology based differentiated approach to the selection of the lexical material, which involves the gradation of difficulties in mastering a foreign language vocabulary, is necessary to increase the effectiveness of professionally oriented lexical competence formation.

3. There are the following criteria for the selection of texts on the basis of which the professionally oriented

lexical competence of future specialists is formed: the principle of communication; the principle of comprehensiveness; the principle of difficulty; the principle of accessibility and availability; the principle of relevance and informativeness; the principle of consistency and gradual formation of understanding; principle of systematization.

4. The main criteria for the selection of professionally-oriented texts are: authenticity of sources; cognition and informativeness; educational orientation; topicality; composite decoration; logical structure; relevant topics; systematic; correspondence of the level of educational, professional and language training of students.

5. As a result of the formation and development of lifelong learning, focusing on the modern content of education, the standards of which should be based on a competency approach and include the formation of common competences, Ukraine will be able to regulate and control the so-called brain drain and turn it into a brain circulation.

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